

Research Article

Mechanism of Action of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. in the Treatment of Endometriosis Based on Network Pharmacology

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Abstract

Background: Endometriosis (EMs) is a prevalent gynecological disorder with unclear pathogenesis, in which abnormal cell proliferation, inflammation, and immune dysregulation play central roles. Traditional Chinese medicine, including *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam., has shown therapeutic potential, yet its mechanisms of action remain poorly elucidated.

Methods: To elucidate the mechanisms of *Toddalia asiatica* against EMs, a network pharmacology strategy was implemented. The active compounds, collected from TCMSP, PubChem, and published literature, underwent filtration based on SwissADME criteria. Potential targets of these compounds were identified via SwissTargetPrediction, and targets associated with EMs were retrieved from GeneCards. The interplay among compounds, targets, and the disease was visualized through a network constructed in Cytoscape. Protein-protein interaction networks were generated using STRING, and functional enrichment analyses (GO and KEGG) were carried

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Citation: Geng Y, Gan J, Li W, Hu J, Zhong L (2026) Mechanism of Action of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. in the Treatment of Endometriosis Based on Network Pharmacology. HSOA J Altern Complement Integr Med 12: 695.

Received: March 23, 2026; **Accepted:** April 02, 2026; **Published:** April 09, 2026

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out with Metascape. The binding affinities of key compounds to their targets were further validated by molecular docking simulations performed with AutoDock Vina.

Results: Our analysis identified 40 active compounds from *Toddalia asiatica*, with 158 corresponding targets predicted. Subsequent cross-referencing with disease databases revealed 40 of these targets were EMs-related genes. Network analysis identified ERBB2, EGFR, mTOR, AKT1, and HIF1A as central hub nodes. KEGG enrichment analysis further showed that these targets were significantly enriched in critical pathways including EGFR, PI3K-Akt, and PD-1/PD-L1 signaling. Finally, molecular docking simulations confirmed that the core compounds—toddacoumalone, magnoflorine, and corytuberine—exhibited strong binding affinities to the respective key targets.

Conclusion: The therapeutic effects of *Toddalia asiatica* against EMs are likely mediated by the modulation of cell proliferation, energy metabolism, inflammation, estrogen signaling, and the immune microenvironment, primarily through the EGFR, PI3K-Akt, and PD-1/PD-L1 pathways. Our findings provide a systematic network pharmacology foundation for its use and highlight promising targets for future experimental validation.

Keywords: EGFR Signaling; Endometriosis; Immune Microenvironment; Molecular Docking; Network Pharmacology; PI3K-Akt Pathway; *Toddalia asiatica*

Abbreviations

EMs: Endometriosis

TCMSP: Traditional Chinese Medicine Systems Pharmacology Database and Analysis Platform

PPI: Protein-Protein Interaction

AKT1: Serine/threonine-protein kinase AKT

mTOR: Serine/threonine-protein kinase mTOR

EGFR: Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1

ERBB2: Receptor tyrosine-protein kinase erbB-2

HIF1A: Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 alpha

GO: Gene Ontology

BP: Biological Process

CC: Cellular Component

MF: Molecular Function

KEGG: Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes

VEGF: Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor

Ang-1: Angiopoietin-1

Introduction

Endometriosis (EMs) is a gynecological condition characterized as the presence and proliferation of ectopic endometrial tissue. With a prevalence of approximately 5–10% [1], its hallmark symptoms—chronic pain, pelvic masses, and infertility—significantly impair patient well-being [2]. The clinical burden of EMs is substantial, often diminishing quality of life and reproductive prospects. Conventional management relies on hormonal suppression and surgical intervention. Nonetheless, limitations including symptom recurrence post-therapy, breakthrough bleeding, and fertility concerns are associated with these options [3,4]. Therefore, identifying novel strategies that are safer, more efficacious, and less prone to recurrence represents a critical unmet need [5-8].

Within the framework of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), EMs falls under the categories of “dysmenorrhea,” “abdominal mass,” and “infertility,” with its fundamental pathogenesis described as “Qi stagnation and blood stasis”. Correspondingly, treatment strategies emphasize activating blood circulation, removing stasis, and regulating menstruation. An increasing number of studies indicate that TCM formulas achieve their effects through multi-component, multi-target, and multi-pathway regulation, influencing inflammation, immune response, endocrine function, and oxidative stress [9-11]. This holistic paradigm may offer comparative advantages over single-target Western medicines in terms of comprehensive symptom management, recurrence reduction, and fertility protection. To bridge TCM theory with modern systems biology, platforms such as the Traditional Chinese Medicine Systems Pharmacology Database and Analysis Platform (TCMSP) have been developed. TCMSP facilitates the systematic identification of active compounds, potential targets, and key pathways of herbal medicines, thereby elucidating their integrative mechanisms [11-13].

Toddalia asiatica (L.) Lam. (abbreviated as *T. asiatica*), a plant of the Rutaceae family, is a herb used in traditional Chinese medicine. Valued for its properties in promoting blood circulation, removing stasis, regulating menstruation, and relieving pain, its root or stem bark serves as the medicinal part. Consequently, it finds wide application in managing dysmenorrhea, amenorrhea, metrorrhagia, rheumatic pain, and traumatic injuries [14]. Given its traditional use in treating gynecological disorders such as dysmenorrhea and amenorrhea, the ethanol extract of *T. asiatica* has been modernly shown to possess anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and other multifaceted bioactivities [15,16]. These properties align with the key pathological features of EMs, suggesting a therapeutic potential that extends beyond its current clinical application in cancer. To scientifically validate and decipher this potential, we applied network pharmacology and molecular docking. This study aims to identify the specific active compounds and molecular targets through which *T. asiatica* may act against EMs, and to map out its integrated mechanism, bridging traditional use with contemporary mechanistic understanding.

Materials and Methods

Screening of *Toddalia asiatica*-related targets

The initial dataset of chemical constituents for *T. asiatica* was compiled from two sources: the TCMSP database [17] (<https://www.tcm-sp-e.com/#/database>) and a targeted literature search. The two-dimensional chemical structures of these constituents were constructed using ChemDraw (version 21.0.0). To identify compounds with

drug-like properties, the structural files were submitted to the SwissADME web tool (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>) for pharmacokinetic profiling and filtering. Subsequently, the potential protein targets of the filtered active compounds were predicted using the SwissTargetPrediction server (<http://www.swisstargetprediction.ch/>). Finally, the predicted targets were normalized, and redundant entries were removed by querying the UniProt knowledgebase (<https://www.uniprot.org>).

Screening of potential therapeutic targets for EMs

Potential therapeutic targets for endometriosis (EMs) were retrieved from the GeneCards database (<https://www.genecards.org/>). In this database, a target’s relevance score quantitatively reflects its association with the disease, with a higher score indicating a stronger association. To focus on the most relevant targets, a score greater than 1 was set as the screening threshold.

Construction of PPI Network for *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. Components and Endometriosis Targets

The common therapeutic targets of *Toddalia asiatica* and EMs were identified by intersecting their respective target sets using the Jvenn online tool (<https://jvenn.toulouse.inrae.fr/app/example.html>), which also provided a visual Venn diagram. The resulting intersection targets were imported into the STRING (<http://version10.string-db.org/cgi/input.pl>) database to generate a PPI network. The network was constructed under the following parameters: organism, *Homo sapiens*; minimum required interaction score, “highest confidence” (>0.9); all other settings, default. This PPI network was subsequently analyzed in Cytoscape 3.10.0 with the MCODE plugin to perform topological analysis, identify key functional protein clusters, and explore their potential biological roles.

Construction of the “*Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. -Active Ingredient-Shared Targets-EMs» network

A network diagram integrating *Toddalia asiatica*, its active constituents, their intersection targets with EMs, and the disease was established in Cytoscape 3.10.0. Topological analysis of this network was then performed using the software’s built-in tool, with parameters such as Degree, Betweenness Centrality, and Closeness Centrality being calculated. These topological indices were employed to filter the network nodes, aiming to identify core therapeutic targets and principal efficacious compounds, thereby facilitating the interpretation of their specific roles in the intervention of EMs by *T. asiatica*.

Functional and Pathway Enrichment Analysis of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. Components and EMs Targets

Functional enrichment analysis, including GO and KEGG pathways, was performed on the common targets using the Metascape platform (<https://metascape.org/gp/index.html#/main/step1>). A p-value threshold of < 0.01 was applied to determine statistical significance. The enrichment results were graphically represented using the Weishengxin online tool (<http://www.bioinformatics.com.cn>) [18].

Molecular Docking Validation

Based on degree centrality within the network, the top five hub targets were prioritized for molecular docking. The UniProt database (<https://www.uniprot.org>) was queried to obtain their respective PDB IDs, and the experimental 3D structures were downloaded from the

Rank	Name	Tag	Molecular formula	CAS ID	Molecular weight g/mol
	5,7-dimethoxy-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one				
1	(5,7-dimethoxycoumarin)	FLZX1	C11H10O4	487-06-9	206.19
2	bufotalin	FLZX2	C11H10O5	61899-44-3	222.19
3	5,7,8-trimethoxycoumarin	FLZX3	C12H12O5	60796-65-8	236.22
4	cis-deoxyglycocoumarin	FLZX4	C16H16O4	—	272.30
5	gleinadiene	FLZX5	C16H16O4	106940-77-6	272.30
6	glycocoumarin	FLZX6	C16H18O4	17245-25-9	274.31
7	artanin	FLZX7	C16H18O5	96917-26-9	290.31
	8-geranyloxy-5,7-dimethoxycoumarin				
8		FLZX8	C21H26O5	—	358.43
9	toddalolactone enol	FLZX9	C16H18O5	137182-36-6	290.31
10	toddalinone	FLZX10	C16H18O4	4335-12-0	274.31
11	7-methoxycoumarin	FLZX11	C10H8O3	531-59-9	176.17
	6-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-methylbutyl)-5,7-dimethoxycoumarin				
12		FLZX12	C16H19ClO5	15575-50-5	326.77
13	suberosin	FLZX13	C15H16O3	581-31-7	244.29
	8-hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin				
14		FLZX14	C10H8O4	—	192.17
	7-geranyloxy-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one				
15		FLZX15	C19H22O3	—	298.38
	7-geranyloxy-5-methoxy-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one				
16		FLZX16	C20H24O4	—	328.40
17	norbrachylin	FLZX17	C14H12O4	60796-64-7	244.24

18	glycomisin	FLZX18	C15H14O4	483-92-1	258.27
19	brachylin	FLZX19	C15H14O4	6054-10-0	258.27
20	5-methoxyseselin	FLZX20	C15H14O4	31525-76-5	258.27
21	5-methoxy-8-geranyloxypsora len	FLZX21	C22H24O5	17182-52-4	368.42
22	toddalocoumarin	FLZX22	C30H26O8	—	514.52
23	toddalocoumarinquinone	FLZX23	C23H18O7	142878-03-3	406.38
24	toddalocoumarinquinolinone	FLZX24	C31H31NO6	139750-79-1	513.58
25	chelerythrine	FLZX25	C21H18NO4+	34316-15-9	348.37
26	Nitidine (Liangmianzhen alkaloid)	FLZX26	C21H18NO4+	6872-57-7	348.37
27	lemairine	FLZX27	C20H14NO4+	24939-31-9	332.30
28	nitidine chloride	FLZX28	C21H18ClNO4	13063-04-2	383.82
29	oxidized nitidine ketone alkaloid	FLZX29	C21H17NO5	548-31-2	363.36
30	8-methoxychelerythrine	FLZX30	C22H20NO5+	—	378.40
31	chelerythrine chloride	FLZX31	C21H18ClNO4	3895-92-9	383.82
32	norchelerythrine	FLZX32	C20H15NO4	6900-99-8	333.34
33	magnoflorine	FLZX33	C20H24NO4+	2141-09-5	342.41
34	heterodacentrine	FLZX34	C19H21NO4	14140-19-3	327.37
35	(2,3,10,11)-dimethylenedioxyt etrahydroprotoberberine	FLZX35	C19H17NO4	—	323.34
36	11-hydroxy-10-methoxy-(2,3) -methylenedioxytetrahydropro toberberine	FLZX36	C20H19NO5	—	353.37
37	berberine (Huanglian Su)	FLZX37	C20H18NO4+	2086-83-1	336.36
38	N,N'-dicyclohexyl oxalamide	FLZX38	C14H24N2O2	3299-64-7	252.35
39	cyclohexylamine	FLZX39	C6H13N	108-91-8	99.17
40	N,N'-dicyclohexylurea	FLZX40	C13H24N2O	2387-23-7	224.34
41	N-trans-feruloyltyramine	FLZX41	C18H19NO4	66648-43-9	313.35

Table 1: Active Components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam.

This table summarizes the pharmacologically active components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. obtained after ADME property screening, serving as a core basis for subsequent target prediction and mechanism analysis of the herb.

RCSB PDB (<https://www.rcsb.org/>). Prior to docking, protein structures were prepared with PyMOL (<https://www.pymol.org/pymol.html>) and AutoDock Tools (<https://autodock.scripps.edu/>); this involved removing water molecules, adding hydrogens, and converting files to PDBQT format. Docking simulations were then carried out with AutoDock Vina to assess the binding affinities of key *T. asiatica* compounds to these targets. Interactions with calculated binding energies < -5.0 kcal/mol were deemed to represent strong binding.

Results

Acquisition of Targets for Active Components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam

Initially, 120 chemical components were extracted from *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. (Supplementary Table 1). Following the screening of ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion) properties, a total of 41 pharmacologically active components were identified (Table 1), including 5,7-dimethoxycoumarin, bufotalin, 8-formylmettin, and 5,7,8-trimethoxycoumarin. Additionally, 158 potential molecular targets were predicted (Supplementary Table 2).

Acquisition of EMs-Related Targets

A total of 1,476 therapeutic targets for EMs were retrieved from the GeneCards database. Subsequently, a screening threshold of Score > 1 was applied to identify potential targets, yielding a final set of 1,379 candidate therapeutic targets for EMs (Supplementary Table 3).

Construction of the PPI Network for *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. Components and EMs Targets

Intersection analysis was conducted between the screened active component targets of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. and the potential therapeutic targets of EMs. A Venn diagram was generated using the jvenn tool (Figure 1), which revealed 40 common targets in total. These common targets were then imported into the STRING platform for PPI network construction (Figure 2 & Supplementary Table 4). Based on network topological analysis and supported by relevant literature, the top five core targets with the highest significance were identified (Table 2 & Figure 3), namely Serine/threonine-protein kinase AKT (AKT1), Serine/threonine-protein kinase mTOR (mTOR), Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1 (EGFR), Receptor tyrosine-protein kinase erbB-2 (ERBB2), and Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 alpha (HIF1A).

Results of the *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. -Active Components-Common Targets-EMs Network

The “*Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam-active component-common target-EMs” network was constructed using Cytoscape 3.10.0 (Figure 4). Network topological parameters, involving 201 nodes and 384 edges, were calculated using the built-in Network Analyzer tool of Cytoscape (Supplementary Table 5). Based on the degree values, the top 5 core components were identified: toddacoumalone, magnoflorine, corydine, toddaculine, and 5,7-dimethoxy-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (5,7-dimethoxycoumarin). Furthermore, topological analysis revealed that node size was proportional to the degree value. Node shapes in the network represented different entity types: circle for *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam, octagon for EMs, hexagon for active components, and diamond for common targets. Notably, toddacoumalone exhibited the highest degree value and betweenness centrality, indicating that it is a key component of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam in the treatment of EMs (Table 3).

Toddalia asiatica (L.)Lam. **EMs**

Figure 1: Venn Diagram of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. Component Targets and EMs Targets.I.

This figure is designed to systematically screen for overlapping associated targets between the active component targets of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. and the potential therapeutic targets of EMs via intersection analysis. It ultimately identifies a total of 40 overlapping targets between the two sets, providing a foundational basis for the subsequent exploration of core molecular nodes through which *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. exerts its regulatory effects on EMs.

Figure 2: PPI Network Diagram of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. and Ems.

Using the 40 common targets identified in Figure 1 as the basis, this figure further dissects the PPI relationships among these targets and uncovers the functional regulatory network potentially formed by them in the pathological process of EMs.

Rank	Gene symbol	Full name	Uniprot ID
1	AKT1	Serine/threonine-protein kinase AKt	P31749
2	mTOR	Serine/threonine-protein kinase mTOR	P42345
3	EGFR	Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1	P00533
4	ERBB2	Receptor protein-tyrosine kinase erbB-2	P04626
5	HIF1A	Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 alpha	Q16665

Table 2: Top 5 Core Targets of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. for EMs Intervention.

This table focuses on the 5 key core targets, each of which is accompanied by standardized identifiers, including gene symbols, full names, and UniProt IDs.

Figure 3: Hub Targets Diagram of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. for EMs Intervention.

This figure represents the result of in-depth mining of the PPI network in Figure 2, and is intended to screen for hub targets that play critical regulatory roles in the EMs pathological network from the 40 common targets, so as to focus the research priorities.

Figure 4: Network Diagram of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam.-Active Components-Common Targets-EmS.

This figure was constructed using the bioinformatics visualization software Cytoscape 3.10.0.

Within the network, node size is positively correlated with degree value (i.e., nodes with higher degree values appear larger in the figure). Different types of entities are distinguished by nodes of distinct shapes, with specific rules as follows:

- Circle: Represents *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam;
- Octagon: Represents endometriosis (EMs);
- Hexagon: Represents active components;
- Diamond: Represents common targets.

Rank	Gene symbol	Full name	Uniprot ID
1	AKT1	Serine/threonine-protein kinase AKt	P31749
2	mTOR	Serine/threonine-protein kinase mTOR	P42345
3	EGFR	Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1	P00533
4	ERBB2	Receptor protein-tyrosine kinase erbB-2	P04626
5	HIF1A	Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 alpha	Q16665

Table 3: Characteristic Parameters of Network Nodes for Main Active Components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam.

This table presents the results of topological parameter calculation for Fig. 4, conducted using the built-in Network Analyzer tool of Cytoscape. Based on degree value and betweenness centrality—an indicator for measuring the “bridging role” of nodes in the network, where a higher value denotes a more critical role of the node in connecting other nodes—the top 5 core active components were identified. These components are as follows: toddacoumalone, magnoflorine, corydine, toddaculine, and 5,7-dimethoxy-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one.

Enrichment Analysis of Target Functions and Pathways

Signal pathway analysis of the potential therapeutic targets of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. for EMs was performed using the Metascape database platform, and the results were visualized via the WeShengX-in platform, a domestic bioinformatics visualization tool. A total of 791 terms were obtained from the Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis, including 691 biological process (BP) terms, 54 cellular component (CC) terms, and 46 molecular function (MF) terms (Supplementary Table 6). The analysis indicated that the potential targets of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam are mainly enriched in the following biological processes: cellular response to organonitrogen compounds, response to inorganic substances, protein autophosphorylation, and cellular response to growth factor stimuli. The main cellular components involved include the extracellular matrix, membrane side, membrane raft, chromosomal region, and neuronal cell body. Additionally, the related targets exhibited significant enrichment in the following molecular functions: protein kinase activity, kinase binding, protein tyrosine kinase activity, monooxygenase activity, and insulin receptor substrate binding (Figure 5).

In parallel, Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway enrichment analysis identified a total of 106 terms (Supplementary Table 7), with key signaling pathways including: Pathways in cancer, EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor resistance, Endocrine resistance, Proteoglycans in cancer, and PI3K-Akt signaling pathways (Figure 6).

Based on the top 20 pathways ranked by P-value and further integration with relevant literature, we inferred that *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. may exert its therapeutic effects on EMs by modulating the following mechanisms: core cancer pathways and therapeutic resistance; the PI3K-Akt signaling network; cell migration and microenvironment remodeling; immune escape regulation; and hormone and endocrine regulation.

Molecular Docking

The top 5 active components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam with the highest degree values in the “*Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam - active component - common target - EMs” network were selected as ligands. Correspondingly, the top 5 core targets with the highest degree values

Figure 5: Results of GO enrichment analysis.

This figure presents the results of pathway analysis for potential therapeutic targets of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam in the treatment of EMs, which were visualized using WeShengXin, a domestic bioinformatics visualization tool, based on data from the Metascape database platform.

Figure 6: Top 20 KEGG pathways sorted by P-value in enrichment analysis.

This figure illustrates the results of KEGG pathway enrichment analysis on the potential therapeutic targets of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam in treating EMs.

were chosen as receptors for molecular docking. The binding energies between the key active components and core targets were calculated using AutoDock Vina, and the detailed docking results are presented in figure 7.

	AKT1	EGFR	MTOR	ERBB2	HIF1A		
toddacoumalone	-6.8	-8.6	-7.0	-6.5	-8.1		0
magnoflorine	-6.3	-7.9	-6.8	-6.0	-6.8		-3
corydine	-6.7	-8.2	-6.2	-6.1	-7.4		-6
toddaculine	-7.9	-10.1	-7.7	-7.5	-9.4		-9
5,7-dimethoxy-2H-chromen-2-one	-5.4	-6.6	-5.5	-5.3	-5.9		-12

Figure 7: Heatmap of molecular docking binding energies.

This figure displays the molecular docking results between the core active components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam and key targets related to endometriosis (EMs). Specifically, the top 5 active components of *T. asiatica* with the highest degree values in the “*T. asiatica* (L.) Lam–active component–common target–EMs” network were selected as ligands, while the top 5 core targets with the highest degree values were chosen as receptors for molecular docking. The binding energies between these main active components and key targets were calculated using AutoDock Vina, and the docking results are summarized in figure 7.

(Note: The numbers in the squares represent the molecular docking binding energies between the horizontal label and vertical label corresponding to each square, with the unit of kcal/mol.)

The docking analysis revealed that the core targets AKT1, EGFR, mTOR, ERBB2, and HIF1A formed stable binding interactions with the five key components, with all binding energies lower than -5 kcal/mol. Notably, EGFR exhibited strong binding affinity toward toddacoumalone, magnoflorine, corydine, and toddaculine, whereas HIF1A showed high binding affinity with toddacoumalone and toddaculine. The top four docking complexes with the most favorable binding energies were further visualized using PyMOL, as illustrated in figure 8.

Figure 8: Representative molecular docking diagrams.

This figure displays the top 4 docking complexes with the most favorable binding energies were selected and visualized using PyMol. Among them, Panel A represents the binding of EGFR to toddaculine, Panel B represents the binding of HIF1A to toddaculine, Panel C represents the binding of EGFR to toddacoumalone, and Panel D represents the binding of EGFR to corydine.

Discussion

Endometriosis (EMs) is a common gynecological disorder characterized by progressive dysmenorrhea, menstrual irregularities, chronic pelvic pain, and impaired fertility. Although pathologically benign, EMs displays several malignancy-like features, including tissue invasion, uncontrolled cell proliferation, local infiltration, distant metastasis, and high recurrence rates. For these reasons, EMs is often regarded as a benign disease with malignant biological behaviors [19].

Current mainstream treatments for EMs in Western medicine mainly consist of conservative hormonal therapy and surgical resection for large endometriotic cysts. Hormonal drugs can effectively relieve pain associated with EMs; however, symptoms frequently recur after drug discontinuation [20-22]. Moreover, long-term hormonal interventions carry risks of adverse effects and potential impacts on fertility [23]. In comparison, surgical treatment can directly remove visible lesions, but complete eradication of ectopic tissues remains difficult, and intraoperative damage to adjacent organs may occur. Accumulating evidence has confirmed that resection of ovarian endometriotic lesions significantly impairs ovarian reserve [24], which is particularly distressing for patients with fertility needs. Additionally, the 5-year postoperative recurrence rate of EMs-related pain can reach 40%–50% [25].

Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) offers unique advantages in the management of EMs, such as alleviating clinical symptoms, improving pregnancy rates, reducing adverse reactions, and lowering recurrence rates [26]. *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. is a representative traditional ethnic medicinal herb, whose primary chemical constituents include coumarins, alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, and phenolic acids. Among these components, coumarins exert notable anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects, whereas alkaloids display antitumor activities [27,28].

In this study, 41 bioactive components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. were screened, corresponding to 158 therapeutic targets, among which 40 common targets overlapped between the herb and EMs. The key active components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. potentially responsible for its anti-EMs effects were preliminarily identified as toddacoumalone, magnoflorine, corydine, and others.

Previous studies have demonstrated that toddacoumalone significantly inhibits PDE4, thereby attenuating systemic inflammatory responses [29,30]. Magnoflorine exerts anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effects by regulating the MAPK, NF- κ B, and PI3K/Akt signaling pathways. Meanwhile, it can suppress tumor cell proliferation via the miR-410-3p/HMGB1/NF- κ B axis [31-33].

Molecular docking validation further revealed that the active components (including toddacoumalone and magnoflorine) displayed strong binding affinities with the core targets ERBB2, EGFR, mTOR, AKT1, and HIF1A. Among these interactions, EGFR showed the strongest binding affinity for toddacoumalone, followed by HIF1A.

AKT1 (protein kinase B, PKB) is a pivotal serine/threonine kinase and a central transducer in cell survival signaling [34]. It regulates cell survival and apoptosis-related proteins through phosphorylation. Importantly, abnormal overactivation of AKT1 is frequently observed in various malignant tumors, including breast, cervical, ovarian, lung, and colorectal cancers [35-39].

EGFR belongs to the HER family of transmembrane glycoproteins and possesses intrinsic tyrosine kinase activity. It primarily mediates the RAS/RAF/MEK/ERK and PI3K/AKT signaling pathways, which are essential for cell cycle progression and apoptosis [40,41].

EGFR also modulates tumor angiogenesis by regulating the expression of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and angiopoietin-1 (Ang-1). Notably, upregulated EGFR expression has been detected in numerous malignant tissues, including breast, lung, pancreatic cancer, and glioblastoma [42-46].

mTOR (mammalian target of rapamycin) is an indispensable serine/threonine protein kinase that plays a central role in regulating cell growth, survival, metabolism, and immune responses. It participates in protein synthesis, nutrient sensing, growth factor signaling, and cell migration [47]. Mounting evidence indicates that dysregulation of the mTOR pathway is closely associated with inflammation, infections, metabolic disorders, cancer, and autoimmune diseases [48-51].

ERBB2 (also known as HER2) is a critical oncogene. The encoded transmembrane glycoprotein regulates cell growth, proliferation, differentiation, and apoptosis [52], and is closely implicated in the initiation and progression of various malignancies, including breast, ovarian, and upper gastrointestinal adenocarcinomas [53-55].

HIF1A (hypoxia-inducible factor-1 α) participates in multiple essential biological processes, including cell proliferation, apoptosis, migration, invasion, angiogenesis, epithelial–mesenchymal transition (EMT), and inflammatory responses [56]. It is frequently overexpressed in tumors and ischemic diseases [57,58].

Notably, EMs shares several pathological hallmarks with tumors, such as abnormal proliferation and angiogenesis [19]. Aberrant activation or overexpression of AKT1, EGFR, mTOR, ERBB2, and HIF1A has been widely reported in EMs lesions [59-63]. These targets are also functionally interconnected within the PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling axis, which acts as a core pathway in EMs pathogenesis [64,65].

GO and KEGG pathway enrichment analyses suggested that *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. may exert therapeutic effects on EMs by modulating cell proliferation, energy metabolism, inflammatory responses, estrogen receptor activity, and the immune microenvironment. Key pathways involved include the EGFR, PI3K/AKT, and PD-1/PD-L1 signaling pathways.'

It has been established that estrogen binds to estrogen receptors and activates downstream mediators shared with the EGFR pathway (e.g., MAPK). Phosphorylation of serine-118 further enhances EGFR signaling and promotes tumor invasion, metastasis, and angiogenesis [66].

In patients with EMs, PI3K/AKT phosphorylation is significantly elevated in endometrial tissues. Blocking this pathway can restore hormonal balance, reduce inflammation, inhibit angiogenesis, and induce autophagy in ectopic tissues, thereby delaying disease progression and relieving symptoms [67].

The PD-1/PD-L1 pathway is critical for maintaining peripheral immune tolerance by suppressing excessive activation of autoreactive T cells and preventing autoimmunity. However, persistent activation of PD-1/PD-L1 inhibits T-cell function, promotes tumor immune escape, and impairs antitumor immunity [68,69]. Additionally, the

PD-1/PD-L1 axis indirectly maintains gut microbiota homeostasis by regulating the Th17/Treg balance. Abnormal activation of this pathway also contributes to the formation of a pro-inflammatory pelvic microenvironment in Ems [70,71]. This multidimensional immunoregulatory network suggests that the PD1/PDL1 pathway may serve as a promising therapeutic target connecting tumor immunity, autoimmunity, and microecological disorders.

Notably, the active components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. identified in this study (e.g., toddacoumalone, magnoflorine) were verified to bind stably to key targets in these pathways (AKT1, EGFR, etc.) via molecular docking, further supporting the notion that *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. treats EMs through a multi-component, multi-target, and multi-pathway mode of action.

In conclusion, *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. may exert therapeutic effects against EMs via a synergistic multi-target mechanism. Its key active components—including toddacoumalone, magnoflorine, corydine, toddaculine, and 5,7-dimethoxycoumarin—act on core targets (AKT1, EGFR, mTOR, ERBB2, HIF1A) and modulate crosstalk among critical signaling pathways, particularly the EGFR, PI3K-AKT, and PD-1/PD-L1 axes. The co-regulation of the PI3K-AKT/mTOR and EGFR pathways may enhance inhibitory effects on the pathological processes underlying EMs, including uncontrolled proliferation, abnormal angiogenesis, excessive inflammation, and immune microenvironment dysregulation, thereby achieving an integrated therapeutic effect.

These bioinformatics predictions preliminarily clarify the potential mechanism of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. in the treatment of EMs and provide a targeted theoretical foundation for future research. Priority can be given to validating high-potential components such as toddacoumalone, which exhibited the highest degree value in network analysis, through in vitro and in vivo experiments.

This study has several limitations. First, the present work is based on network pharmacology predictions without in-depth experimental validation. Second, the active components were screened from public databases, and their pharmacokinetic profiles remain uncharacterized, which may affect clinical efficacy. Future studies will focus on verifying the binding affinities of key components, establishing EMs models to evaluate therapeutic effects, and exploring downstream signaling cascades to support the clinical translation of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. for EMs management.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Our analysis utilized publicly available summary statistics databases, such as TCMSP, Uniprot, and GeneCards. No new data were collected, and no new ethical approval was required.

Consent for Publication

Not applicable

Availability of data and materials

The chemical components of *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. were obtained from the TCMSP (<https://www.tcmsp-e.com/#/database>), as well as relevant literature searches. The therapeutic targets of EMs were derived from the GeneCards database (<https://www.uniprot.org>). All data analyzed in this research can be accessible freely through the corresponding websites.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

This study was supported by the Natural Science Research Project of Guangxi University of Chinese Medicine. (Grant No.2024MS052).

Author's Contribution

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Acknowledgement

All authors thank the patients and sequencers who provided samples and the publicly available databases.

Supplementary Tables

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